

Book Review

Xavier, Basis S. *Philosophies of Margins: Theoretical Foundations and Illustrative Models of Application*. Madurai: Shanlax Publications. ISBN: 978-93-90082-36-0 pp. xii+ 258. ₹ 650/-

This book, *Philosophies of Margins: Theoretical Foundations and Illustrative Models of Application*, is a collection of articles written during the philosophical journey of the author for more than two and half decades both as a student and a teacher of philosophy. His philosophical passion started towards Karl Marx, Ambedkar, Periyar and structuralism; then towards phenomenology, existentialism, hermeneutics and Wittgenstein and later the interest tuned towards critical theory, post-Marxism and postmodernism. His initial interest as a doctoral scholar on folk philosophy, popular consciousness, identity construction and post-colonialism has been slowly convergent towards ethnophilosophy – the current specialization of the author. Ethnophilosophy is the study of indigenous philosophical systems. The implicit concept is that a specific culture can have a philosophy that is not applicable and accessible to all peoples and cultures in the world; however, this concept is disputed by traditional philosophers.

This philosophical journey or movement is very obvious in all the sixteen papers found in this book. The first article deals with structuralism and Levi-Strauss. Reflective articles on critical theory, Habermass, Gramsci, phenomenology and ethnophilosophy of Africana philosophy are part of the articles. It also includes studies on epistemology of ancient Tamils, illustrative models on anthropological and folklore tools to Dalit consciousness and indigenous knowledge for the digital world. The article also focusses on identity construction of periphery, nomads and postcolonialism, drawn from the insights of Derrida, Foucault and Arunthathiyars. An insightful study on the liberation approaches of Ambedkar and Guitierrez is also included. The final article is tellingly titled, “You are and therefore I am,” focusing on the inclusive nature of ethnophilosophy.

The present author’s philosophical journey is always focused on the dialectics between theory and practice. Eventually when the author encountered with the problems of the poor and the exploited, he was searching for philosophical solutions. While doing philosophy, his mind always looked how to put them into practice. Hence this dialectics of theory-practice is very vital and very

fundamental. His immersion with the life of the subaltern and periphery and their continued suffering constantly provoke for new philosophical solutions. With these conceptual understanding, whenever a new philosophical thought or perspective is emerging, he all the time reflected on how these ideas can be used to unravel the agonies of the oppressed.

Some thinkers and their philosophy come to the rescue when there is a search for answers to some pertinent socio-cultural and philosophical questions. So their theories are briefly exposed in this book in order to understand their relevance to such problems. Some such authors are Habermas, Gramsci, Foucault, Gutierrez Derrida from the Western perspectives and Ambedkar and Arunthathiyars from the Indian soil. Thus theoretical foundations of philosophy (including critical theory, phenomenology and epistemology) are sought in these articles and some illustrative models of application are strived for the liberation of the margins.

The author acknowledges that the Western philosophical search is external whereas the Indian one is internal. That is why reason of the west dominates not only nature, but also other nations and colonies. The Indian reason, on the other hand, pays no attention to the external world of *maya* (p. 95).

The author also indicates the challenge of living in harmony with the other. The very notion of 'us' vs 'them' is dangerous. We tend naturally to include some as 'us' and exclude the rest as 'them,' the 'other'. (p. 250). Then he borrows from Sudhir Kakar's psychology of exclusion where the other may belong to different ethnic, language, race, caste and religious groups. The difference leads to the construction of the other and the difference becomes a reason for discrimination, oppression and domination (p. 252), instead of accepting, acknowledging and respecting the other. The other may be both physical and mental and is demonized (p. 252).

By promoting unity and not uniformity, communities can live in harmony. The relation between harmony and identity is explored in the last section of the book. This leads to a deeper understanding of the philosophy of the other, inspired by Nelson Mandela, Jean-Paul Sartre, Gabriel Marcel, Emmanuel Levinas and Martin Buber (pp. 254-255).

The theology of the other bases itself on the prophetic proclamation of God's interest in the other. It also recalls Jesus' commitment to the other when non-Jews were generally regarded as the other. The prophetic parable of the good Samaritan is brought up to indicate Jesus' desire "to include the excluded" (p. 256). Through his psychological, sociological, philosophical and theological analysis, the author attempts to provide a new vision of the other, especially from the perspectives of the poor, dalits, trials, women and minorities. Thus he shows the way to achieve harmony with the 'other' by the mantra, "You are, Therefore I am!" (p. 257).

–Kuruvilla Pandikattu

Pandikattu, Kuruvilla. (2021). *Finding God in Everything: Insights into Finding Everything in God*. New Delhi/Pune: ISPCK/Jnana Deepa. ISBN: 978-81-947592-3-2 pp. xvi + 250 ₹350/-

Some of the questions this book attempts to answer are: Who are we? How can we relate to other and thereby realise ourselves? What is the meaning of my life? Where do we find God? How do we relate to Him? How does genuine spirituality enable me to become truly human, joyous and authentic?

These are some of the issues the author takes up in this book on contemporary, creative spirituality. This book invites us to find God in everything. More, it invites us to find everything in God. It deals primarily with life as lived out in our daily lives in our interaction with things and God. Then it tries to draw spiritual insight from the events of daily life, so that we can life up our lives, to embrace the world, fellow-human beings and God. The approach that we take in this book is an inclusive and dialogical one, where we try to discern the divine in every aspect of the earthly life.

So, we normally begin with a concrete experience, person, book or experiment. From that we go to explore the larger dimensions of life and study the deeper values inherent in it. So, we move from the material to the spiritual, from the mundane to the perfect, without in any way sacrificing the material or the mundane.

The author believes that our spirituality emerges from the earthly, without in any way giving up the other-worldly. He holds that true joy and happiness comes from the simple pleasures of life. We hope that our fulfilment as human beings starts from our concrete experiences of joy, sadness, relationships and love.

In the First Part of this book, the author tries out different ways and means of reaching happiness and healing. He wants to show that our friends, relationships, memories and forgiving the harm others have done to us will enhance our well-being and bliss. The next Part talks of the spiritual dimensions of our day to day life, which allows us to experience genuine joy. Meditations, mindfulness and other means of spiritual experiences are referred to in this part.

The Third Part invites the readers to foster creativity through art, silence and music, which form part of the melodies of our lives. Here we realise that our spiritual life has be rooted in the earthly and bodily aspects of our lives. This takes us to the next Part, dealing with the spiritual practices leading to joy and optimism.

The abandonment that is critical to any spiritual life takes us to the next Part, nurturing the aesthetic dimension of our lives. Art, dance, curiosity as well as reading and writing can make our life more authentic and empathetic. The Sixth Part helps us to explore some of deepest human values and try to make the best

of the encounters that we human beings are capable of: encountering fellow human beings, the world and the whole of reality face to face. The next part describes the role of stories in healing, liberating and making our lives genuinely humane.

Part Eight talks of individual responsibility to the society and the need to pay attention to the joys and sorrows of the larger political, scientific and social dimension of our collective reality. The next part deals with our responsibility to make of this world a better one, recognising the larger (and at times, uncomfortable) truths of our social life.

The final Part of the book deals with meaning and integrity within myself and in the larger world and cosmos we live in. It talks about the human need to be true to one's own self and to lead a modest and human life, so that we can truly feel at home with ourselves.

Thus, this book believes that the God we seek (or conversely and even better, the God who seeks us continuously) is to be found in everyone and everything. He is present in everywhere and traces of Him can be found in all things at all times, if we are attentive enough. That loving God is always present to us. From this experience, everything and everyone gets a different value. Then everyone has to be seen in God and everything has to be experienced in the Divine. So, we are called to find Everyone and Everything in God. That is grace! Such a God is unconditional love and unqualified mercy.

This book indicates that the spiritual can be traced in all activities, earthly, mundane and secular. It assumes that we can only reach the spiritual in and through the secular, the ordinary experiences of normal human beings. All in all, this is a modest attempt to reflect on our contemporary lives and see the glimpse or traces of the Divine in our lives. It is an invitation to discern God's presence in everything and in everyone. It is a simple effort "to see God in everything." And further "to find everything in God" as St. Ignatius of Loyola would put it.

Though this book is derived from the Ignatian insight, it is a book on Ignatian spirituality or Spiritual Exercises. It is highly recommended for seekers of all spiritual traditions and students of philosophy and theology. **-Gini George**

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